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INVESTIGATING HOW THE FMCG INDUSTRY EMPLOYS DESIGN-DRIVEN APPROACHES: THE DICHOTOMY BETWEEN LITERATURE AND PRACTICE.

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, there has been a growing discourse regarding the emergence of a new role for design, one that involves design thinking and design-driven innovation. This new role affirms design integration into the all the organisational activities required for strategic deployment. However, there has been little research looking at how such approaches are employed and can influence the transformation of culture within a specific industry situation.

According to the fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) industry *status quo*, organisations demand fuel to ignite the transformation of brand development. Therefore, the main argument of this paper involves diagnosing the current phenomena by comparing the literature and practice in the FMCG industry. The findings from a comparative analysis explain how an organisation can embrace design-driven approaches in its brand development system. This paper contributes to developing brands in the FMCG industry through integration with design-driven approaches.

Keywords: a new role for design, design integration at strategic level, FMCG brand development

INTRODUCTION

Design research faces a new era, with its focus shifting from the process of developing artefacts to the transformation of organisations through design integration. Much design research has sought to substantiate the benefits of the usage of design and the engagement of users: winning by design (Walsh et al., 1992); value-chain creation through design (Mozota, 2003); the development of consumers' experience (Press & Cooper, 2003); design

management in branding (Montaña et al., 2007) and the development of emotional engagement with consumers (Gobé, 2001). These indications call for design integration at strategic level in order to impact on the entire activities within organisations and societies to achieve synergy in developing tangibles. This new role for design enables cooperative interaction with evolved notions of branding; specifically, 'the living brand' and 'holistic branding' currently emphasize that branding is not just a matter for the marketing or design departments but should involve the entire organisation (Ind, 2007; Ind & Bjerke, 2007; Schmidt, 2002). By aligning with a new branding paradigm, the new role for design creates opportunities for design to be integrated into branding in order to develop experience and value. Abbing (2010) asserts that employing design is a substantial attribute in the effective deployment of strategic brand development.

To attain this new role for design, researchers have started to highlight new approaches or methods of design - 'design thinking' and 'design-driven innovation'. Researchers claim that these new approaches can provide competitive advantage through experiences in developing products and brands and implementing them across entire organisations (Verganti, 2009, 2008; Brown, 2009, 2008; Esslinger, 2009; Martin, 2009; Neumeier, 2008). These new approaches can be defined as design-driven approaches: a combination of conceptual and practical designerly approaches in order to find a new role for design. In other word, design-driven approaches can be applied from operational level to strategic level in both design

related projects and not-design related projects. However, even though notions of design-driven approaches are currently highlighted as a form of design thinking or design-driven innovation, there has been little empirical research looking at how design-driven approaches are employed and can influence the transformation of culture in a specific industry situation.

This research investigates the features of design-driven approaches in the Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) industry. Compared to other industries, the characteristics of FMCG brand development are constrained by the manufacturing and launching of products (packaging). The other constraint is limited capacity for integration of internal and external parties for the brand development process (Page & Thorsteinsson, 2011). Further more, Olins (2007) claims that in the recent years, the FMCG industry having lost out on initiatives to find ways of developing brands. Despite all the constraints, FMCG brand development is less highlighted and investigated within academia. Thus, this paper will discuss the following questions:

- 1) What design-driven approaches are identified in the literature?
- 2) How are design-driven approaches employed in practice within the FMCG industry?

To substantiate the evidence to answer the questions, firstly, through a content analysis, design-driven features at different levels - cultural, strategic, and tactical/operational - were identified. Secondly, based on the identified features, a survey (conducted with corporations and consultancies involved in FMCG brand development) explicates how design-driven approaches are employed in the FMCG industry. Thirdly, a comparative analysis of theoretical and empirical findings suggests a framework for employing design-driven approaches in the FMCG industry.

FEATURES OF DESIGN-DRIVEN APPROACHES FROM THE LITERATURE

Currently, without the articulation of a new role for design, this is already *ad hoc* in academia. Corporations abuse it as a tool for marketing without

manifesting and implementing it into their organisations. Thus, this section intends to describe explicitly design-driven features from the literature.

PROCEDURE FOR THE CONTENT ANALYSIS

A selection of books is drawn from the literature, which are grounded in design-driven innovation (DDI) and design thinking (DT). To explore these features, the seven books and authors' papers were used as key sources: Berger (2009); Verganti (2009); Brown (2009); Martin (2009); Esslinger (2009); Neumeier (2008); and Lafley & Charan (2008). These are highly recommended in a design-thinking discussion in LinkedIn, and highly cited, are starting points. The selection process then branches out in two respects: business vs. design; and with specific viewpoints (innovation or specific disciplines) vs. general design empowerment. Figure 1 illustrates the different stances of seven books, which vary in terms of how to bridge the gap(s) between design and business (practices) and deliver design-driven approaches to audiences.

Figure 1. Relationship between Design-Driven Aspects from the Literature

Because the ways of adopting a stance are situated differently, it is necessary to clarify which theme arises from the features collected. Instead of explicating features within prescribed themes, a more emphatic approach is to attempt to seek insights. These themes are attributes for composing design-driven culture.

FEATURES OF DESIGN-DRIVEN APPROACHES FROM THE LITERATURE

By exploring the literature, features can be appreciated with respect to the following two substantial themes: 1) designerly application: provide ways for designers' exploration and exploitation within organisations; 2) design endorsement: change the conventional behaviour of organisations, such as sales-driven and short-term effectiveness. To bridge the two themes, the other primary theme is unifying the first and second attributes for a design-driven culture: i.e. collaborative activities to develop competitive advantage by bridging the gap between design and business contexts. In addition, to enhance the three previous themes, the human resources theme arises in the literature. Under these four themes, specific features are categorized into strategic level and tactical (operational) level. These themes are illustrated in Figure 2 which shows the primary attributes to consist of design-driven culture and shows the relationship between the themes.

Figure 2. Relationship of Primary and Booster DDA Themes

Each theme and feature is delineated in detail below. Firstly, themes will be illustrated.

- **Designerly Application (DA):** This theme indicates the features which help to stimulate mechanisms to embed the application of designerly ways, beyond a limited design development process, as a way of undiluted design-driven approaches in design thinking and the design-driven innovation literature. It focuses on exploring the prospective possibilities of the challenges facing organisations and solving them in designerly ways.
- **Design Endorsement (DE):** Simply providing designerly ways of doing things cannot achieve a

design-driven culture. This requires design integration at the corporate strategic level. Thus, the intention of this theme relates to how business endows authority to designerly exploration and exploitation in order to embed them throughout an organisation as a core value.

- **Collaboration (CO):** The above two cultures often confront paradoxical situations, because some features in the two cultures are contradictory or run in parallel. Collaboration calls for an integrated way, both internally and externally, to bridge the gap between designerly application and design endorsement.
- **Human resources (HR):** Each person's behaviour is composed of every culture's activity, internally or externally. In order to transform the habitual attitude toward designerly exploration and exploitation, it is imperative to engrave design-driven culture on employees' minds.

The four themes form the epicentre for a design-driven culture in an organisation. While the first two themes are primary, the last two themes can be regarded as boosters for primary themes. However, "the major challenge of cultural change is that culture is transformed through actions" (Ind and Bjerke, 2007: 189). Ind and Bjerke (2007: 189) state that "actions determine the nature of the culture and the culture determines the ability to notice movements in the environments" - 'a double loop process'. Therefore, the next features resonate with mechanism for actions, which achieve the fulfilment of design-driven culture. Subordinated features of primary themes are categorized into design-driven approaches and design endorsement approaches (see Figure 3).

Firstly, strategic features in design-driven approaches can be divided into two primary approaches: research mechanism of exploration and mechanism for exploitation.

- **Research mechanism for exploration:** This enables organisations to understand / identify people's needs and desires and explore ideas incrementally and radically with designerly applications.

- **Mechanisms for exploitation:** These are twofold - 1) create design mechanisms for exploitation using abductive thinking and integrated thinking at strategic level, 2) radically experiment with ideas generated.

Secondly, strategic features in design endorsement are categorized into two primary features.

- **Strategic decision-making in organisations:** It is necessary to develop a strategic decision-making process and trigger a bottom-up process to engage in designerly applications.
- **Strategic design integration in organisations:** It is necessary to establish design-endorsed environments into organisations within a business context.

Lastly, booster themes - Collaboration and HR - are interventions between design-driven approaches and design endorsement approaches.

- **HR management:** This is twofold: 1) education to enhance the capacity of creativity and understand designers' approaches in organisations, 2) developing a mechanism to allocate design-driven people and to collaborate with different disciplines in an organisation.
- **Platform for collaboration:** In a complex business context, it is necessary to develop a platform for internal-external collaboration.

These clusters of strategic features resonate with tactical/operational features regarding the specific methods in Figure 3. These subordinated features at the strategic level exemplify specific performances to fulfil higher levels of performance. Each method at the tactical (operational) level and the mind-sets toward themes are taken account in a design-driven culture organisation and are applied in the questionnaire for the survey.

Figure 3. Summary of Design-Driven Themes and Subthemes

FEATURES OF DESIGN-DRIVEN APPROACHES IN THE FMCG INDUSTRY

Based on the identified themes and their features, a survey questionnaire was developed. However, considering the limited space for this paper, only some of the questions (variables) are being presented: a descriptive analysis of the eighteen variables for corporations and sixteen variables for consultancies from the five-rating scale questions (RSQs), and the five variables from the categorical scale questions (CSQs). This survey intended to interrogate two primary stakeholders - corporations and consultancies - regarding how to understand and employ DDA features as confirming each other's opinions about design-driven approaches to brand development. The survey was structured in two sections

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Online survey methods were applied for the respondents' convenience. Sampling was based on FMCG corporations and consultancies that operate businesses in the UK. However, there is no category relating to FMCG and their consultancies in UK National Statistics or in other statistics publications. In spite of this circumstance, to attain representative sampling, cluster sampling is employed in this research among the sampling skills within probability sampling; there are two strata to list organisations. Firstly, corporations are listed by

looking at different ranges of brands in UK supermarkets and drugstore websites and their stores: Sainsbury and Boots. This list is categorised into two subsets: global, and the EU & UK as well as surpassing various FMCG industries and sizes of organisations. Since FMCG corporations tend to have more than one brand, when FMCG corporations are listed, the number of corporations is not identical to the number of brands. 162 organisations are listed as FMCG corporations. Consultancies, which are relevant to FMCG clients, were selected from the directory of the Design Business Association (DBA) and the Institute of Practitioners in Advertising (IPA) in the UK. 80 branding consultancies, which won DBA Design Effectiveness Awards and have strong relevance to FMCG, were identified from the DBA directory. Employing the same extraction method, advertising consultancies were also listed. The last tier seeks to identify what positions and disciplines exist within these organisations. This identification is attained and transferred into the indicators of profiling questions.

PROFILING OF RESPONDENTS

Table 1 illustrates respondent numbers and details for each section of the survey. In the survey of corporations, 40 people from among 61 respondents completed the first section online (65.6%), and 27 people among those 40 respondents to the first section completed the second section (67.5%). In the survey of consultancies, 33 people from among 56 respondents completed the first section (58.9%), and then 26 people among those 33 respondents to the first section completed the second section (78.8%).

	Section 1	Section 2
Corporations (61)	40	30
Consultancies (56)	33	27

Table 1. Participants' Number

Corporation profiling can be summarized by the following characteristics:

- Respondents are from Food & Beverages, Personal Care, and Household - typical 'FMCG industry' (74%);
- 67.5% of them operate businesses in over 10 countries;

- 87.5% of them account for over 250 employees: large and established corporations (adapted from the categories and definitions of SMEs used by the EU (cited in Krake, 2005));
- 52.5% of them account for marketing departments;
- 72.5% of them account for marketers or brand managers for ownership of brand development.

The characteristics of consultancies in this paper are illustrated below:

- 57.6% of respondents account operate businesses in over 6 countries;
- They work in diverse-sized consultancies;
- 45.5% of them account for design departments;
- 75.8% of them account for a marketer or brand manager for ownership of brand development.

RESULTS FOR RATING SCALE QUESTIONS (RSQ)

This discussion in this section proceeds in the following order: 1) corporation RSQ and 2) consultancy RSQ.

Before discussing the results of the RSQ in detail, the parameter of the extent of concurrence needs to be explained. The parameter, which is applied here, is arbitrary, with the following rationale. A variables mean is used as a gauge of the parameter (Figure 4). The rating range from 1 to 5 - rarely, less often, sometimes, often, always - is divided into the five units by increments of 0.8. A variable mean between 1 and 1.8 accounts for 'strongly disagree (SD)' with the literature; a mean between 1.81 and 2.60 is 'disagree (D)'; a mean between 2.61 and 3.40 is 'neither agree nor disagree (N)'; a mean between 3.41 to 4.2 is 'agree (A)' and a mean between 4.21 to 5.0 is 'strongly agree (SA)'.

Figure 4. Gauge of the Parameter for Concurrence between FMCG Industry and the Literature.

Firstly, the corporation RSQ will be discussed. Table 2 illustrates the concurrence of design-driven approaches (DDA) features between the practices of FMCG industry and the literature. According to the previous profiling of corporations, it can be asserted that this summary accounts for a large part of established FMCG industry.

The variables 'adopting stage-gate' and 'educating employees on DDA' fall into 'strongly agree' and 'disagree' with the literature. In terms of stage-gate processes, Petrie (2008) indicates that the success of a stage-gate process stems from a formal structure in which the delivery of product is the priority within business. This entails FMCG industry concentrating on delivering products via a formal structure. However, a strong stage-gate process works against DDA organisational structure in the literature; the literature claims flexibility in organisations.

The following variables - utilising external experts, flexible organisational process, designers' working across departmental boundaries, communicating with consultancy and evaluation of projects - fall into 'agree' with the literature. 'Working across departmental boundaries' falls into the 'strongly agree' group. There is no variable in the DA theme which falls into the 'agree' or 'strongly agree' group. All the other variables fall into the 'neither agree nor disagree' group, these variables account for a negative kurtosis value. This indicates that there is

variability in the data.

Overall, 6 variables among the 18 account for concurrence with the literature and the other 12 are not prevailing features. The variables in the 'disagree and strongly disagree' group are features which hinder cultivating attitudes to design-driven approaches. Comparatively, most variables for designerly application and designerly endorsement fall into the 'neither agree nor disagree' group. It can be asserted that attitudes in these themes are regarded differently according to the context where an organisation operates. Some interesting results were found:

- 1) Although respondent organisations utilise a strong stage-gate process, paradoxically, variables in the 'agree and strongly agree' groups are drawn on. It can be assumed that variables in the 'agree and strongly agree' groups do not convey the same meaning as the literature or utilize a certain way within a stage-gate process.
- 2) 'Educating DDA' accounts for a small value and this may result in respondents' attitudes in the DA theme aligning with the variables in the DE theme.
- 3) 'Working across departments' and 'designers' working across departmental boundaries' account for 'strongly agree' and 'agree'; on the other hand, 'designer placement outside department' accounts for 'neither agree nor disagree'. Thus, this implies that designers tend to be placed in a

Concurrence	Theme	Variable	Mean	SD
Strongly disagree	DE	Adopting a stage-gate process	4.38	0.774
Disagree	HR	Educating employees on DDA	2.43	1.152
	DA	Embracing DDA	2.90	1.215
	DA	Using an iterative approach	3.03	1.310
	DA	Completing all phases of exploratory projects	3.10	1.081
	DA	Regarding constraints as challenges	3.40	0.982
Neither agree nor disagree	CO	Designer placement outside the design department	2.75	1.149
	DE	DDA's contribution at strategic level	3.08	1.309
	DE	Consideration that design is a core driver	3.00	1.219
	DE	Leadership support for the integration of DDA	2.90	1.128
	DE	Management of design impact on brand development	3.23	1.025
Agree	HR	Creative capability in recruitment	2.98	1.387
	CO	Utilising external experts	3.78	0.947
	DE	Flexible organisational process	3.45	1.154
	CO	Designers working across departmental boundaries	3.78	1.050
	CO	Communicating with consultancies	4.05	0.846
Strongly agree	HR	Evaluation of projects	3.60	1.033
	CO	Working across departmental boundaries	4.25	0.927

Table 2. Summary of Rating Scale Variables - Corporations

Concurrence	Theme	Variable	Mean	SD
Strongly disagree	n/a	n/a		
Disagree	DE	Adopting a stage-gate process	3.52	0.906
	HR	Educating employees on DDA	2.42	0.902
Neither agree nor disagree	DA	Embracing DDA	3.24	0.830
	DA*	Using an iterative approach	3.12	0.857
	DA	Completing all phases of exploratory approaches	2.82	0.950
	DA*	Regarding constraints as challenges	3.18	0.808
	DE*	Leadership support for the integration of DDA	3.00	0.866
	DE*	Flexible organisational process	2.82	0.846
	CO*	Working across departmental boundaries	3.33	0.816
	CO	Designers working across departmental boundaries	3.12	0.992
	HR	Creative capability in recruitment	2.70	1.262
	HR*	Evaluation of projects	3.03	0.951
Agree	DE	DDA's contribution at strategic level	3.42	1.032
	DE	Consideration that design is a core driver	3.48	0.939
	DE	Management of design impact on brand development	3.73	0.977
	CO	Communicating with consultancies	3.70	0.951
Strongly agree	n/a	n/a		

Table 3. Summary of Rating Scale Variables - Consultancies

structured department and rarely fit into an interdisciplinary team or a marketing team.

- 4) Variables which fall into the ‘agree and strongly agree’ group are attitudes towards exploiting projects not perceiving and cultivating DDA. This indicates that, overall, DDA is perceived as conventional design (creating tangible output).

Secondly, the consultancy RSQ will be discussed. This seeks to triangulate the corporation results through consultancies’ views. Table 3 illustrates the concurrence of consultancies’ opinions about their clients. Two variables - ‘utilising external experts’ and ‘design placement outside design department’ - are excluded from questions asked to consultancies, because it is hard for consultancies to provide opinions on these variables. There is no value in the ‘strongly agree and disagree’

groups. Only two variables - adopting a stage-gate process and educating employees on DDA - fall into the ‘disagree’ group. Both consultancies and corporations draw on these two variables, going against the literature. Four variables - DDA’s contribution at strategic level; consideration that design is a core driver; management of design impact on brand development; communicating with consultancy - fall into the ‘agree’ group. All the other variables belong to ‘neither agree nor disagree’ group. The variables with “*” in the table refer to a positive kurtosis value - implying variability. While all the variables in the corporations’ ‘neither agree nor disagree’ have negative kurtosis values, which indicates a wide dispersion of values, the variables with “*” indicate that the majority of respondents are around the centre point of ‘sometimes’. Even though these variables do not have a wide dispersion,

	Designery application				Collaboration		Design endorsement						Collaboration			Human resources		
DDA Features	Embracing DDA	Using an iterative approach	Completing all the phase of exploratory projects	Regarding constraints as challenges	Utilising external experts	Designer placement outside design department	Adopting a stage-gate process	DDA's contribution at strategic level	Consideration that design is a core driver	Leadership support for integration of DDA	Management of design impact on BD	Flexible organisational process	Working across departmental boundaries	Designers working across departments	Communicating with a consultancy	Educating employees on DDA	Creative capability in recruitment	Evaluation of projects
Literature	N	N	N	N	A	N	SD	N	N	N	N	A	SA	A	A	D	N	A
	N	N	N	N			D	A	A	N	A	N	N	N	A	D	N	N

Corporations Consultancies

Table 4. Summary of Rating Scale Variables

consultancies perceive that all the variables in the ‘neither agree nor disagree’ group do not prevail features in clients’ organisations and brand development. The variables, except for ‘communicating with consultancy’ in the ‘agree’ group, are abstract attitudes towards DDA employment. Thus, it may be assumed that respondents in consultancies may not generalise clients’ attitudes but reproduce what they claim regarding importance of design.

In summary, this consultancy survey indicates that except for the variables in the ‘agree’ group, the respondents from the consultancies consider that the features of DDA do not prevail with their clients. Also, they account for the ‘agree’ or ‘strongly agree’ groups more than corporations do, as evaluating corporations’ attitudes toward DDA perceptions and exploitation of DDA.

Overall, there are two common results in the corporation and consultancy results for the RSQs (Table 4). 1) Both groups draw on ‘adopting a stage-gate process’ and ‘educating employees on DDA’ in the ‘strongly disagree and disagree’ group, thus these two variables are not employed in FMCG industries well. 2) All the variables in the DA theme within corporations and consultancies fall into the ‘neither agree nor disagree’ group. This indicates

that no features of the DA theme prevail in FMCG industries. Thus, it can be assumed that to cultivate the features of DA, education on DDA results in embedding the features in DA.

RESULTS FOR CATEGORICAL SCALE QUESTIONS (CSQ)

All the indicators for the categorical scales data are driven by the literature and respondents were asked to select three indicators for each variable. While the previous RSQ analysis informs about attitudes towards DDA features, CSQ frequency analysis entails findings on how FMCG industries exploit DDA features. As a way of displaying the indicators in this paper, depending on the number of indicators for each variable, three or four indicators which are ranked as high or low frequency are displayed (Tables 5 and 6).

Corporation Categorical Scale Variables

The CSQ of corporations are discussed. On the whole, indicators that fall into the ‘high’ group are twofold: 1) indicators directly relating to delivery of a product or a brand and 2) indicators that are very abstract in nature. That is to say, even though corporations acknowledge the role of design, they do not employ specific DDA features in order to develop brands and nurture a DDA culture within organisations.

	High	Low
Design methods in brand development (DA)	1) Customers act as a trigger for brand development (16) 2) Brainstorming for ideas (15) 3) Consumer journey mapping (11) 4) Iterative process (8)	1) Persona (0) 2) Cultural probes (1) 3) Participatory development process (3) 4) Scenario building (3)
Approaches to exploratory brand development (DA)	1) Emphasis on finding new directions for brands (20) 2) Responsive to new technology (11) 2) Responsive to new trends (11) 3) Challenging constraints (10)	1) Curiosity in projects (0) 1) Self-confidence (0) 2) Intuition (1) 2) Open critique of ideas (1) 2) Flexibility within projects (1)
Approaches for design to be integrated at strategic level (DE)	1) Perception that design can create value (23) 2) View design as investment not a cost (16) 3) Balance between design and business (14)	1) Pride in your organisation’s culture of design (3) 2) Risk-taking for new approaches 3) Employees’ willingness to embrace design-driven approaches (7) 3) Legitimate commitment to design (7)
Approaches for designers to collaborate with other departments (CO)	1) Multidisciplinary team (24) 2) Co-location (13) 2) Mutual interaction (13)	1) Confidence in your own discipline (4) 2) Trust each other (5) 3) Foster the free flow of ideas (9)
Approaches to enhance employees’ creativity (HR)	1) Continuing professional development (21) 2) Interdisciplinary collaboration (18) 3) Hire creative people (14)	1) Financial incentives (6) 2) Open work space (9) 3) Empower design performance (11) 3) Inspiring work space (11)

Table 5. Summary of Categorical Scale Variables - Corporations: (n) Value of Indicators

The findings are illustrated below:

- 1) Design methods in brand development (DA): Customers are regarded as an important trigger but ways of exploiting this are ambiguous and abstract. Specific methods to utilise DDA fall into the ‘low’ group. In contrast to the literature, prototyping, visualisation and story telling are also not prevailing approaches.
- 2) Approaches to exploratory brand development (DA): Feasibility and the possibility of delivering tangibles are regarded as a determinant feature to conduct exploratory approaches. They are not interested in enhancing mind-sets to undertake exploratory projects.
- 3) Approaches to design integration at strategic level (DE): Even though corporations acknowledge that design can create value, indicators, which are highly ranked, are abstract. Respondents in corporations rarely draw on the specific indicators which need to exploit design’s contribution at strategic level.
- 4) Internal collaboration (CO): Corporations acknowledge the influence of designers’ collaboration and draw on more physical features (co-location and multidisciplinary team) rather than a motivating mind-set.
- 5) Approaches to increase creativity (HR): Open and inspiring workspace, empowering design

performance and financial incentives are not regarded as important factors to enhance employees’ creativity.

Secondly, Table 6 displays consultancies’ opinions on which approaches corporations utilise and what factors influence brand development in their clients’ organisations.

- 1) Design methods in brand development (DA): The methods for employing DDA seem to fall into methods of ideas generation. Even though this result is confused by the consultancies’ working style, prototyping, which is an agile way of utilising DDA within the literature, is not considered a main method in practice. It can be assumed that consultancies use visualisation instead of employing prototyping.
- 2) Approaches to exploratory brand development (DA): Feasibility and the possibility of the delivery of a product or a brand immediately are regarded as important features, but indicators which are grounded in the culture are rarely considered to be utilised in exploratory projects.
- 3) Approaches to design integration at strategic level (DE): Even though consultancies have an opinion that corporations acknowledge that design can create value, they do not legitimate DDA in order to enhance each employee’s understanding and embracing of it. That is to say,

	High	Low
Design methods in brand development (DA)	1) Customer's act as a trigger for brand development (14) 1) Visualisation (14) 2) Brainstorming of ideas (12) 3) Consumer journey mapping (11)	1) Open-end process (0) 2) Scenario building (1) 2) Out-of-the-box thinking (1) 2) Participatory development process (1)
Approaches to exploratory brand development (DA)	1) Emphasis on finding new directions for brands (18) 2) Responsive to new trends (13) 3) Responsive to new technology (8) 4) Challenge constraints (6)	1) Self-confidence (0) 1) Iterative process (0) 1) Curiosity in projects (0) 2) Optimistic approach (1)
Approaches to design integration at strategic level (DE)	1) Perception that design can create value (22) 2) View design as investment not a cost (19) 3) Balance between design and business (14)	1) Risk-taking for new approaches (1) 2) Legitimate commitment to design (2) 3) Employees’ willingness to embrace design-driven approaches (3) 3) Pride in your organisation’s culture of design (3)
Approaches for designers to collaborate with other departments (CO)	1) Multidisciplinary team (18) 2) Foster free flow of ideas (17) 3) Open debate (11)	1) Confidence in your own discipline (4) 2) Co-location (6) 3) Trust each other (7)
Approaches to enhance employees’ creativity (HR)	1) Continuing professional development (20) 2) Interdisciplinary collaboration (15) 3) Hire creative people (13)	1) Financial incentives (2) 2) Open work space (7) 3) Empower design performance (11)

Table 6. Summary of Categorical Scale Variables - Consultancies: (n) Value of Indicators

consultancies consider that corporations are not keen on nurturing DDA at strategic level.

- 4) Collaboration (CO): To enhance designers' collaboration, flexible ideas initiation and open debates are selected as important attributes.
- 5) Human resources (HR): Financial incentives, open workspace and empowering design performance are not regarded as important factors to enhance employees' creativity.

To summarise both the corporation and consultancy CSQ results, FMCG industries rely on consumers a lot. These approaches can be seen as the frailty of developing out-of the box thinking and aligning that with analytical thinking. Consumers can spark initiatives but this is not demand to develop breakthrough products or brands (Beverland, 2010; Verganti, 2009). The indicators which corporations and consultancies draw on are abstract perceptions of design, not specific methods. It can be inferred that FMCG industries acknowledge design's contribution but do not have chances to experience specific DDA methods and realise the benefits of DDA. Therefore, it is necessary for FMCG industry to have opportunities to encounter DDA methods through projects or education.

CONCLUSION

All data are intended to triangulate so that the results need to be woven together to provide a complete picture. There are some overarching findings presented below:

- **RSQ DA:** All the DA variables for both corporations and consultancies fall into the 'neither agree nor disagree' group. This indicates that there is variability of perception of design's contribution and design's support at strategic level. In this theme, as associated with the education DDA in the HR theme, It can be assumed that there is a lack of HR for DDA views and employees do not have chances to learn and experience DDA benefits, beyond the benefit of creating final tangibles through HR or projects. To create DDA culture, each employee is important as part of the culture. Hence, it is necessary to provide education for DDA's sake or to encourage

designers or design thinkers to engage with other disciplines via project exploitation.

- **RSQ DE:** Only one variable, flexible organisational process, falls into the 'agree' group in the corporation DE variables; on the other hand, consultancies draw on more variables in the 'agree' group within the DE theme. The consultancies consider that their clients have a certain understanding of design's contribution and benefits at strategic level, but the corporation survey shows there is variability in the variables. This may cause some problems in collaboration between corporations and consultancies. Also, in order to improve DE attitudes, FMCG industry needs to be convinced that DDA can create value in developing tangible outputs as well as transforming organisations into being design-driven. In the corporation survey, although corporations utilise strong stage-gate processes, they consider that they utilise flexible organisational processes well. This indicates the following two points: 1) FMCG industry has a rigid organisational structure in how it sees utilising a strong stage-gate process. 2) FMCG industry utilises flexibility within a stage-gate process. Aligning profile and sizes of corporations, it can be inferred that large corporations utilise flexible processes within stage-gate processes. However, this survey does not provided how organisations utilise flexible processes within a strong-stage gate process. Therefore, this finding needs to be interrogated in terms of to what extent the use of flexibility occurs within the stage-gate process, because in terms of the consultancy survey, consultancies have similar opinions on stage-gate processes but different opinions on the flexibility of processes; there may be variability in these variables.
- **RSQ CO:** More variables in the CO theme fall into the 'agree' group, but consultancies have different opinions on corporations' collaboration; consultancies draw on variables that are paired to corporations in the 'neither agree nor disagree' group except for one variable, communication with consultancies. From the corporations' perspective, collaboration is utilised well in their organisational structures, because the variable

‘designer placement outside the design department’ falls into ‘neither agree nor disagree’. Thus, this implies that designers tend to place in a structured department and rarely fit into an interdisciplinary or marketing team.

- **RSQ HR:** Educating DDA on employees is rated low by both corporations and consultancies and falls into the ‘disagree’ group. It indicates that education on DDA rarely takes place in corporations.

Throughout the survey, consultancies evaluate the variables higher in the DE theme but lower in the CO theme. In addition, consultancies only evaluate the variables highly for consultancies. Overall, DDA in corporate organisations is not utilised well. Half of the variables fall into ‘neither agree and disagree’ and this indicates that there is variability within each variable. Subsequent analysis is necessary to identify what causes respondents opinions to be varied.

While RSQs provide attitudes towards DDA approaches, CSQs enable triangulation of the RSQs. Synthesizing the two sets of results provides these findings:

- **RSQ+CSQ:** Throughout CSQ, FMCG industry perceives that DDA is an abstract, not a concrete, way to apply to their organisations. This indicates that DDA, though manifested as strategic, are not underpinned for exploitation, thus DDA are perceived in a conventional manner within FMCG industry. FMCG industry tends to employ approaches to impact directly on developing output for exploratory approaches. An interesting point is that both prototyping and visualisation do not fall into the high ranked group, and prototyping also does not fall into the high ranked group for consultancies. This indicates that the method - making an idea visible, which is claimed by design research (e.g. Brown, Martin, Berger, etc.) - is rarely utilised in FMCG industry. This draws out a question whether this is relevant method to FMCG industry or not. In addition, it is necessary to interrogate this situation in the further research.

Throughout the survey, attitudes and methods from the four themes do not hold together as identified in the literature (Figure2). Some attitudes and methods seem to be missing because of the nature of FMCG industry or its propensity to neglect DDA. However, the literature’s claims are not manifested in a specific industry context and do not substantiate pragmatic evidence for implementing DDA into business. These both tendencies result in dichotomy between FMCG practice and literature. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a mechanism for employing and utilising DDA in FMCG industry. The next subsection suggests some implications of imbuing DDA features into FMCG industry.

SUGGESTIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

To pave the fractures and attain the ideal DDA employment, some initial directions arise:

- **1) Experience through projects or education:** According to the literature, DDA features are organic and interdependent. One small change will be embedded and impact on the entire organisation. Hence, it is imperative to identify and know where DDA begins and how to imbue DDA into FMCG organisations. Thus, it is necessary for designers and/or consultancies to provide DDA experience or methods through projects or continuing to develop education in order to expand DDA capability beyond conventional design (small ‘d’)
- **2) Visionary leadership for DDA integration:** FMCG industry employs DDA for exploratory projects and it has to prove some impact on corporations within 12 months (exploratory timeframe in brand development: corporations 62.5% and consultancies 78.8%). However, it needs patience to embed DDA into organisations and to produce positive results in a corporate culture. Hence, visionary leadership for DDA is necessary to cultivate DDA in business-driven organisations and projects.
- **3) Reformulate stage-gate process for DDA utilization:** It seems inevitable to keep stage-gate processes in large corporations so it is imperative to develop a way utilising DDA within a stage-gate process: for example, examining how to utilise flexibility and DDA dynamically at certain stages.

- **4) Diverse disciplines' early involvement:** Early decisions on brands and products continue so the latest new or diverse DDA methods do not get chance to be used in the early stages. This seems to prevent corporations breaking with their typical approach. Thus, an interdisciplinary team or designer's involvement at an early stage can help to resolve this complication.

LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

There are three limitations to this paper. Firstly, even though people from diverse departments and different sizes of companies were contacted, respondents came only from departments (e.g. marketing, design, branding) that are directly involved in brand development and most of these are from large companies. Therefore, it is necessary to interrogate how smaller corporations and other departments (sales, manufacturing, etc.) understand and exploit DDA. Secondly, there is no variable for asking about DDA performance results with regard to corporate growth. Since it was uncertain that all respondents would recognize or access this information, this was excluded from the survey. Hence, it will be investigated in further research. Thirdly, due to limitations of space, the researcher cannot provide a contrast between different subgroups' profiling. Subsequent further analysis will be able to inform how different groups understand and employ DDA and enable the formulation of suggestions on how to start igniting DDA more specifically.

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